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HOW TO WIPE OUT THE CHALLENGES OF INFORMATION PRIVACY AND INTEGRITY BY USING RIC PROTOCOL AND PMOW SCHEME IN CLOUD COMPUTING

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Abstract:

Among so many definitions of cloud computing, the most probable accepted definition should be as ‘Cloud computing is a facilities given model that enables with convenient, on-demand network access with shared pool of well configured computing resources like services, applications , servers, storage and network) that should be rapidly provisioned and deliver with minimal cost & management effort’. The privacy issues in cloud computing are noticed, especially the privacy and security challenges for data security in the cloud storage. The main problem is to define and assign keys to users are key concerned. To minimize this problem a proposed scheme is effectively based on the observations that are in practical application situations. The security and privacy requirements are formally well defined and the achievable proposed scheme is proven secure under a normal assumption in the standard model. A privacy-preserving RIC protocol which achieves public verifiability & authenticity without disclosing any stored information is proposed.

Keywords: *Cloud computing, Data integrity & Privacy, RIC protocol, PMOW scheme.*

Introduction

There are so many definitions were attempts to define cloud computing in many different ways. Among all the definitions, the most probable accepted definition should be as Cloud computing is a facilities given model that enables with convenient, on-demand network access with shared pool of well configured computing resources like services, applications ,

servers, storage and network) that should be rapidly provisioned and deliver with minimal cost & management effort.

There are five essential characteristics of the cloud model [MG09]:

1. **Rapid elasticity:** This means that the computing capabilities should be assigned with any demanded quantity and can be elastically provisioned to cloud users.
2. **Service on demand:** The cloud users are able to use on-demand services for instances network storage & server time without any human interaction between cloud users and service providers.
3. **Location independence:** It means that by using multi-tenant model, The computing resources must be pooled up to serve multiple users. Really it is independent from exact location that the cloud users have no knowledge about the same.
4. **Measuring service:** Measuring services means to keep the services in controlled, monitored, about the resources that have been provided to the cloud users.

. The Privacy issues in cloud computing includes:

- 1) Data security
- 2) Identity and access control
- 3) Key management
- 4) Virtual machine security

Among these main security issues in the cloud, data security and integrity is believed to be the most difficult problem which could limit the use of cloud computing [RTSS09]. In fact, access control and key management are all issues involved in data security. Data security in the cloud refers to data confidentiality, integrity, availability and traceability (CIAT), and these requirements pose major problems for cloud computing. Data confidentiality requires that information be available or disclosed only to authorized individuals, entities or IT processes. Data integrity ensures that the data is maintained in its original state and has not been intentionally or accidentally altered or deleted.

In Section II, system model and adversary model are described in background , related work is described in section III and in section IV Proposed system presented and conclusion is shown in section V.

Motivations and Contributions and challenges:

This paper addresses data security challenges in the cloud storage. Security mechanisms are having the design to ensure any leakage free of data in cloud environment.

Key Management: Data encryption before outsourcing to the cloud is a common and simple way to protect data privacy. Although the encryption algorithms are public, information encrypted under these algorithms is secure because the key use to encrypt the remains secret. The classical tree-base hierarchy schemes such as RFC2627 [WHA99] and the scheme proposed by Wong *et al.* [WHA99],

Access control: Access control techniques are very different in cloud computing because the cloud servers are not seen as trustworthy by most cloud users, especially large enterprises and organizations. Yimercati *et al.* [Dvfj⁺07b] proposed an access control scheme for securing data stoppage on untrusted servers based on key derivation methods [AFB05]. In their scheme, the owner created corresponding public tokens to grant access for a user. With his secret key, the user was able to derive decryption keys for design files.

Searchable Encryption Techniques: As the data is usually encrypted before being outsourced to cloud servers, how to search the encrypted data in the cloud has recently gained attention and led to the development of searchable encryption techniques. This problem is challenging however, because meeting performance, system usability and scalability requirements is extremely difficult. However, oblivious RAM is also commonly considered to be impractical due to its overhead. Suppose the client stores n data files in remote storage, and then each data request is replaced by $O(\log^4 n)$ or $O(\log^3 n)$ requests. Additionally, $O(n \cdot \log n)$ external memory is required in order to store the n data files.

Remote Integrity Check: Storing data in remote cloud servers has become common practice..

The latest verification schemes concentrated on the problems of securing data integrity at remote servers and securing cloud storage applications. These schemes can be classified into ‘Proof of retrievability’ (POR) schemes (e.g., [JJ07, BJO09, DVW09, SW08]) and ‘provable data possession’ (PDP) schemes (e.g., [ABC⁺07, ABC⁺11, EKPT09]). A POR scheme is a challenge-response protocol. In POR schemes, a cloud provider demonstrates the retrievability to a client. PDP schemes are similar protocols which only detect a large amount of corruption in outsourced data.

It is noticed that Hao, Zhong and Yue’s public RIC scheme [HZY11] provided a security feature against data leakage. They adopted the approach introduced by Sebe *et al.* [SFB⁺08]

to support data dynamics and privacy, but their scheme requires the verifier to be in possession of all the homomorphic tags used for the integrity check. Therefore, it increases costs for storage and communication. In addition, although they prove that the public verifier cannot learn the target data, the tags themselves can leak some information about the data.

To overcome these problems, a privacy-preserving RIC protocol which achieves public verifiability without disclosing any information is proposed.

Proof of Ownership: Proof-of-ownership (POW) is closely related to two other similar problems: proof of retrievability (POR) and proof of data possession (PDP). POR schemes [JJ07], [SW08], [BJO09], [D VW09], [ZX11] are challenge-response protocols. In POR schemes, a cloud provider demonstrates the file retrievability to the client. PDP schemes [ABC⁺07],[ABC⁺11],[EKPT09],[SFB⁺08],[FB06], [SBD⁺04], [WWL⁺09, WWRL10, WWR⁺11, ZB12, YOA07] are similar protocols which only detect a large amount of corruption in outsourced data. The main difference between POW and POR/PDP is that the latter usually uses a pre-processing step on the client side while the former does not.

Framework

The framework for public remote integrity check in clouds is first described, as shown in Figure a.1. The public RIC protocol checks that the cloud storage retains the out sourced data file M which can be divided into chunks of data blocks m_i 's. Prior to outsourcing the data file, the data owner O pre-processes that m/s and generates several homomorphic verifiable tags T_i 's. Then the owner O out sources his file M and all the tags T_i 's to cloud storage and deletes them in local database. The data format of M is independent here and it could be an encrypted file. Later, the owner O outsources the periodic task of checking data integrity to some third party verifier V . The third party verifier sends a challenge to the cloud server S and asks S to respond based on the stored data blocks as well as the tags. Upon successful completion of the protocol, V is convinced that the data file M has not been altered or deleted by S . To conduct the protocol, V is only required to know the public key of the data owner. In addition, no information about the data blocks nor the tags are revealed to V . This framework is designed for the purpose of the data owner O who wants to outsource the periodic task of data integrity checking, but does not want to leak his/her data at the same time.

Threat Model: The cloud server S must answer the challenges from the third party verifier V . Failing to do so represent a data loss. However the cloud server is not trusted, that is to say, the cloud server may try to convince the verifier that it possesses the file even though the file is totally or partially missing. The cloud server may have several motivations for

misbehavior. For example, the server may want to reclaim storage by discarding data that has not been or is rarely accessed, or hide some data loss incidents due to management errors and hardware failures. The third party verifier V must verify the integrity of the out sourced data. The third-party verifier may not be fully-trusted as well. That is, the verifier may try to retrieve the owner's data through the process of verification.

Figure a.1: The framework of public Remote Integrity Check in cloud storage.

A public remote integrity check protocol has to detect the cloud server's misbehavior when the server has deleted a fraction of the file. Moreover, it has to ensure that the third party verifier cannot learn any out sourced data through executions. Discarding data that has not been or is rarely accessed, or hide some data loss incidents due to management errors and hardware failures. The third party verifier V must verify the integrity of the out sourced data. The third-party verifier may not be fully-trusted as well. That is, the verifier may try to retrieve the owner's data through the process of verification. A public remote integrity check protocol has to detect the cloud server's misbehavior when the server has deleted a fraction of the file. Moreover, it has to ensure that the third party verifier cannot learn any out sourced data through executions.

Research Analysis

Formal Definitions

Definition 1.1 (Public Remote Integrity Check Scheme) A public RIC scheme consists of

two polynomial-time algorithms (*Key Gen*, *TagGen*) and an interactive protocol (*Proof*) that captures the properties including data possession and public verification without disclosing data.

KeyGen. This algorithm is run by the data owner. It takes a security parameter k as input and outputs a pair of matching public and secret keys (pk, sk) .

TagGen. This algorithm is run by the data owner to generate the homomorphic tags for the data chunks. It takes as inputs a public key pk , a secret key sk and a data block m_i , outputs the homomorphic tag T_i for this data block m_i .

Proof. This is a pair of interactive algorithms (*Proofs*, *Proofv*) executed by the cloud server and a public verifier respectively. The input of **Proofs** is a public key pk , a set of data blocks and homomorphic tags $\{ m_i, T_i \}$. The input of *Proofv* is a public key pk . Upon completion of the protocol, **Proofv** outputs 1 if the proof is accepted and 0 otherwise.

Definition 1.2 (Correctness) A public remote integrity check scheme is correct if for all key pairs (pk, sk) output by *KeyGen*, for all the tags T_i output by *TagGen* with input m_i, sk , **Proofv** with input pk outputs 1 if it is interacting with **Proofs** with input $pk, \{ m_i, T_i \}$.

The Proposed Scheme

Main Construction

Let $e : G \times G \rightarrow G_T$ be a computable bilinear map with $|G| = |G_T| = p$ for some large prime p . Let g, g_1, g_2, u and v be generators of G . The scheme also employs a hash function $H : \{0,1\}^* \rightarrow G$, viewed as a random oracle. Details of the construction of a hash function whose range is the group G has been described in [BLS01]. The main construction of the proposed scheme is as follows: **KeyGen.** Select a random $x \in \mathbb{Z}_p$, this algorithm generates the public key as (g^x, g, g_1, g_2, u, v) . The secret key is x . **TagGen** $((sk, m_i) \rightarrow T_i)$. Before generating the tags, the data file M is preprocessed into n data blocks $m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n \in \mathbb{Z}_p$. In the following each data block will be referred as m_i for $1 \leq i \leq n$. This algorithm then generates a homomorphic tag T_i , for data block m_i , where $T_i = (H(i) \cdot u^{m_i})^x$

Proof. The pair of algorithms **Proofs**, **Proofv** interacts as follows.

Proofv chooses a set of data blocks for challenge. Let $I \subset \{1, \dots, n\}$ be the index set for the blocks to be challenged. **Proofv** randomly chooses $c, d \in \mathbb{Z}_p$, computes $D = g_1^c g_2^d$. **Proofv** randomly picks $a_j \in \mathbb{Z}_p$ for $j \in I$ and sends $I, \{a_j\}_{j \in I}, D$ to **Proofs** as the challenge.

Proofs computes $T = \prod_{j \in I} T_j^{a_j}, \sum_{j \in I} a_j m_j, B = e(u, g^x)$ and $C = e(g_1, g)$. **Proofs** then randomly chooses $r, s, t, t_p, t_t, t_s \in \mathbb{Z}_p$ and computes

$$T_p = u^{t_p} \cdot v^{t_r}, T_Q = g_1^{t_t} \cdot g_2^{t_s},$$

$$T_A = B^{t_p} \cdot C^{t_s}, P = u^{\rho} \cdot v^r,$$

$$Q_1 = T \cdot g_1^s, \quad Q_2 = g_1^t \cdot g_2^s$$

- **Proofs** sends $(T_p, T_Q, T_A, P, Q_1, Q_2)$ to **Proofv**.
- **Proofv** sends (c, d) to **Proofs**.
- **Proofs** checks if $D = g_1^c g_2^d$ and computes

$$z_p = t_p - c \cdot \rho, \quad z_r = t_r - c \cdot r$$

$$z_t = t_p - c \cdot t, \quad z_s = t_s - c \cdot s$$

and sends (z_p, z_r, z_t, z_s) to **Proofv**.

- **PV** outputs 1 if and only if all the following equations hold

$$T_p \stackrel{?}{=} P^c \cdot u^{c\rho} \cdot v^{z_r}, \quad T_Q \stackrel{?}{=} Q_2^c \cdot g_1^{z_t} \cdot g_2^{z_s}$$

$$T_p \stackrel{?}{=} \left[\frac{e(Q_1, g)}{e(\prod_{j=1}^l H(j)^{a_j}, g^x)} \right]^c \cdot B^{z_p} \cdot C^{z_s}, j \in I$$

Otherwise 0.

A Brief Explanation of The Proposed Protocol

Note that a tuple (T, ρ) satisfying the equation

$$e(T, g) = e(\prod_{j \in I} (H(j)^{a_j}) u^x, v)$$

is a proof-of-retrievability of the messages $\{m_j\} j \in I$ according to [SWOB]. Instead of requiring the cloud server to send (T, ρ) to the verifier (which leaks information about the data), the protocol **Proofs** is modified so that it is a zero-knowledge proof-of- knowledge of the tuple (T, ρ) satisfying the above equation. Indeed, the message flow $\rho = (D, (T_p, T_Q, T_A, P, Q_1, Q_2), (c, d), (z_p, z_r, z_t, z_s))$ can be viewed as a zero knowledge proof-of-knowledge of such a tuple. Intuitively, the proposed protocol is secure if [SWOB] is a secure proof-of-retrievability and that ρ is a zero-knowledge proof-of-knowledge protocol with soundness. **A Public RIC System**

Now a public RIC system can be constructed as Figure 6.2, from the above scheme in three phases: *Setup*, *Challenge* and *Proof*. It should be emphasized that the cloud server does not send back to the verifier any of the data file blocks and not even their sum.

Additionally, the third-party verifier checks the integrity of the outsourced file without having the secret key. In particular, the third-party verifier does not retrieve any information about the data even when the challenge only consists of a single block.

Security Analysis

Two security requirements are identified for the proposed scheme. The first one regards *data possession*. Specifically, an adversary cannot successfully construct a valid proof without possessing all the blocks corresponding to a given challenge, unless it guesses all the missing blocks. The second one is to capture *public verification without disclosing data*. No third party verifier should be able to retrieve any data or tag information in probabilistic polynomial time. To formalize this notion, it is required that for any verifier, a PPT simulator can be constructed to simulate the view of the verifier without the knowledge of the messages and homomorphic tags.

- **Setup:** The data owner o invokes the algorithm $KeyGen$ to generate a pair of matching public and secret keys (pk, sk) . o then invokes $TagGen$ for all data blocks $(1 \leq i \leq n)$ and sends all the homomorphic tags T_i 's to the cloud server S , along with pk and m_i 's. o may now delete the original data file M and all the tags T_i 's from his local storage .
- **Challenge:** The third-party verifier V requests remote integrity check for l distinct blocks of the data file M with $(1 \leq i \leq n)$:
 1. V generates a challenge $chal = \{(j, a_j) \mid 1 \leq i \leq l, a_j \in \mathbb{R} \mathbb{Z}_p\}$ and sends $chal$ to S .
 2. S computes $(T_p, T_Q, T_A, P, Q_1, Q_2)$ as follows: $T_p = u^{t_p} \cdot v^{t_s}$, $T_Q = g_1^{t_t} \cdot g_2^{t_s}$, $T_A = B^{t_p} \cdot C^{t_s}$, $P = u^\rho \cdot v^r$, $Q_1 = T \cdot g_1^s$, $Q_2 = g_1^t \cdot g_2^s$ where $T = \prod_{j \in I} T_j^{a_j}$, $\rho = \sum_{j \in I} a_j m_j$, $B = e(u, g^x)$ and $C = e(g_1, g)$. $(T_p, T_Q, T_A, P, Q_1, Q_2)$ is returned to V .
 3. V generates a random challenge c .
 3. S computes $z_p = t_p - c \cdot \rho$, $Z_r = t_r - c \cdot r$, $Z_t = t_t - c \cdot t$, $Z_s = t_s - c \cdot s$, and returns (z_p, Z_r, Z_t, z_s) to V .

Proof: V checks the integrity of the outsourced data without either having the data or the secret key sk :

1. V computes $A = \frac{e(Q_1, g)}{e(\prod_{j=1}^l H(j)^{a_j}, g^x)}$.

2. V checks the validity of the proof by verifying whether the three equations 6.1a, 6.1b and 6.1c hold.

Figure 6.2: A Public RIC System.

Data Possession

This requirement is formalized by using a security game played between a challenger C and an adversary A . A public RIC protocol is sound if any cloud server that convinces an honest verifier is in possession of the data file M . Following the definition in [HZY11], it means that there exists an extractor algorithm that can extract the data file M when it is interacting with the cloud server in the public RIC protocol.

Data Possession:

In the DP-game, the challenger C denotes the third-party verifier and the adversary $A = (A_1, A_2)$ denotes a cheating cloud server. The game is divided into two phases, the learning phase and the proof phase.

Setup: The challenger C runs $KeyGen$ to generate a keypair (pk, sk) , and sends pk to the adversary A .

Query: The adversary A can make at most q_s queries to a tag oracle, providing some file block m ; during each query. C then computes all the homomorphic tags T_i and sends them back to A , along with all the m_i 's. The adversary stores all the m_i 's and the corresponding tags T_i 's.

Execute: The adversary A can undertake at most q_e executions of public RIC protocol for any file M that he has made a tag query, with specifying the corresponding T_i 's.

Proof: The adversary A outputs the description of a prover machine P and the set of messages $M \subset \{1, \dots, q_s\}$ to be challenged. C interacts with P in the proof protocol with M being the set of messages to be challenged.

Informally speaking, the data possession property requires that if P can pass through the verification protocol with C , P should be in possession of all messages m_i for $i \in M$. This is formalized as follows.

Definition 2.1 (Soundness) A public remote integrity check scheme is sound if there exists a knowledge extractor K that can recover $\{m_i | i \in M\}$ from the prover machine P with non-negligible probability.

Theorem 1 The construction of a public RIC system captures data possession if Waters public-verification scheme is secure in the random oracle model.

In the following it shows how to construct the extractor K . Note that K will only be used in proofs. It is an algorithm that runs in probabilistic polynomial time on input P , pk and the

index set M . The output of K is the set of messages $\{m_i | i \in M\}$

The knowledge extractor K will work in the following way: If the prover P responds correctly to an initial challenge c , then K will rewind P and issue a different challenge c' for which P also responds correctly. Note that this requires K to have the discrete logarithm of g_2 to base g_2 so that it can issue two different challenges for the same value D . If K can find two such challenges c and c' , then K has the following equations:

$$T_P = P^c \cdot u^{z_p} \cdot v^{z_r} = P^{c'} \cdot u^{z_{p'}} \cdot v^{z_{r'}}$$

$$T_Q = Q_2^c \cdot g_1^{z_t} \cdot g_2^{z_s} = Q_2^{c'} \cdot g_1^{z_{t'}} \cdot g_2^{z_{s'}}$$

$$T_A = A^c \cdot B^{z_p} \cdot C^{z_r} = A^{c'} \cdot B^{z_{p'}} \cdot C^{z_{r'}}$$

Now it can get

$$\text{If denotes } \frac{P^c}{P^{c'}} = \frac{u^{z_p} \cdot v^{z_r}}{u^{z_{p'}} \cdot v^{z_{r'}}}, \quad \frac{Q_2^c}{Q_2^{c'}} = \frac{g_1^{z_t} \cdot g_2^{z_s}}{g_1^{z_{t'}} \cdot g_2^{z_{s'}}}, \quad \frac{A^c}{A^{c'}} = \frac{B^{z_p} \cdot C^{z_r}}{B^{z_{p'}} \cdot C^{z_{r'}}}$$

$$\Delta z_r = z_{r'} - z_r, \Delta z_t = z_{t'} - z_t \text{ and } \Delta z_s = z_{s'} - z_s, \quad \Delta z_{p'} - z_p,$$

from the above equations it can have

$$P = u^{-\frac{\Delta z_p}{\Delta c}} v^{\frac{\Delta z_r}{\Delta c}},$$

$$Q_2 = g_1^{-\frac{\Delta z_t}{\Delta c}} g_2^{\frac{\Delta z_s}{\Delta c}},$$

$$A = B^{-\frac{\Delta z_p}{\Delta c}} C^{\frac{\Delta z_r}{\Delta c}}$$

Then, it has

$$\frac{e(Q_1, g)}{e(\prod_{j=1}^l H(j)^{a_j}, g^x)} = e(u^{-\frac{\Delta z_p}{\Delta c}}, g^x) \cdot e(g_1, g)^{\frac{\Delta z_s}{\Delta c}}$$

Thus K can compute $T = Q_1 \cdot g_1^{-\frac{\Delta z_s}{\Delta c}}$ and $\rho = -\Delta z_p / \Delta c$. In [SW08], it has been proven under the CDR assumption that ρ must be correctly formed. That is, note that ρ is a linear equation of the form $a_1 m_1 + a_2 m_2 + \dots + a_l m_l$. Then by choosing independent coefficients $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_l$ in l executions of the extraction above on the same blocks $m_1, m_2, \dots, m_l$, K can obtain l independent linear equations in the variables $m_1, m_2, \dots, m_l$. Thus K can solve these equations to obtain the data file M that contain blocks $m_1, m_2, \dots, m_l$. The extraction is required to be succeed (with all but negligible probability) from

the prover (adversary) that causes the verifier (challenger) to accept with a non-negligible probability ϵ . Then the extractor K can recover enough blocks to reconstruct the original M from such an adversary will take $O(n/\epsilon)$ interactions.

Public Verification without Disclosing Data

To capture the requirement of public verification without disclosing data, it is required that there exists a PPT simulator S which is capable of simulating the view of any verifier given that the public parameters and the public key of the user as input. In other words, the RIC protocol is zero-knowledge.

Theorem 2 *The proposed public remote integrity check protocol is a RIC protocol is zero-knowledge.*

Proof: In order to prove that the public RIC protocol is a zero-knowledge (ZK) proof system, one needs to prove three properties: completeness, soundness and zero-knowledge.

Completeness: Suppose the honest prover possesses the secret M just as required in *GenProof*. It is straightforward that the prover can always convince the verifier to accept the proof. Thus the perfect completeness condition follows.

Soundness: To show soundness (namely that even an arbitrarily malicious prover P^* cannot convince the verifier V to accept a false statement with more than a negligible probability), how to extract a witness M from two different runs of the proposed protocol is first demonstrated.

Assume there are two different transcripts of the proposed protocol, the extractor K can be constructed in the following way that as described in section 6.4.1. Having $O(n/\epsilon)$ interactions, the extractor K can recover enough blocks to reconstruct the original M from a malicious prover P^* .

In such a case, $T = Q_1 \cdot g_1^{\frac{\Delta z_p}{\Delta c}}$ and $\rho = -\Delta z_p / \Delta c$ can be efficiently computed from the transcripts. Thus it can be concluded that for any first round message $(T_p, T_Q, T_A, P, Q_1, Q_2)$ that P^* may send to V , there is at most one possible challenge c which P^* could answer correctly. Then P^* can effectively compute a witness as above. However P^* must decide upon its first round message before seeing the challenge and therefore will receive the "correct" challenge c with probability at most $1/p$ which is negligible.

Honest Verifier Zero-knowledge. To show that the proposed protocol is zero-knowledge, it is necessary to describe an efficient simulator S that interacts with any verifier, and produces an interaction that is indistinguishable from the verifier's interaction with the

prover.

- S randomly picks $z_p, z_r, z_t, z_s, \in R Z_p, P, Q_1, Q_2 \in R G$ and computes the following values:

$$T_p = P^c \cdot u^{z_p} \cdot v^{z_r}, \quad T_A = \left[\frac{e(Q_1, g)}{e(\prod_{j=1}^l H(j)^{a_j}, g^x)} \right]^c \cdot B^{z_p} \cdot C^{z_r}$$

$$T_Q = Q_2^c \cdot g_1^{z_t} \cdot g_2^{z_s},$$

- S sends $T_p, T_Q,$ and T_A to the verifier.
- The verifier sends the values $I, \{a_i\}, D$ to S.
- S randomly picks and sends $T'_p, T'_Q, T'_A, P', Q'_1, Q'_2 \in R G$ to the verifier.
- The verifier returns (c, d) to S.
- S validates $D = g_1^c, g_2^d$, and rewinds the verifier to the point when it receives the tuples $(I, \{a_i\}, D)$.

The verifier returns (c, d) to S. Under the discrete logarithm assumption, the values (c, d) will be the same with the first run.

- S returns z_p, z_r, z_t, z_s to the verifier.

Table 1 Comparisons between previous schemes and the proposed scheme.
 {1001: [NWZ12], 1002: [PS12], 1003: [ZX12], 1004: [XCZ13]}

	1001	1002	1003	1004	Proposed Scheme
Proof of ownership	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Privacy	✓	×	✓	✓	✓
Encrypted files	✓	×	✓	×	✓
Joint ownership	×	×	×	×	✓

Technique Preliminaries of PMOW Protocol:

This section starts with the framework designed for multiparty ownership proof in cloud storage, as shown in Figure a.2. The main assignment of **PMOW** protocol is to examine that whether the each user is keeping ownership of the file F . The authenticated client C can encrypts the file by choosing any symmetric key k & produce many ciphertext $CT_i(k)$ for particular user I as $U_i, 1 \leq i \leq n$. Then the client C sends the ciphertext $(CT_F, \{CT_i(k)\})$ to server V of the cloud storage who verifies this with protocol. The server V uses an exact-code R for pre-process to input buffer CT_F & broken (CT_F) into blocks $m_j, 1 \leq j \leq m$. Here each

block is hashed in pairs till the root node H_{root} is achieved.

As shown in Figure a.3. The main purpose of generating Merkle-tree MT_{h_i} , for a short verification of the information v that is the root node of the tree and in such a way the multiple users U_i at a time who shares the file F ownership and thus the users are able to download the ciphertext to decrypt . Now Server V is responsible to send a challenge to each and every user to ask a proof.

Figure a.2: The framework for proof of multiparty ownership in cloud:

When protocol is executed successfully then cloud server understand that every user has the file F . *There is no information about file F is to be revealed to V .*

Figure a.3: Building of the Merkle-Tree

Theat Model. The multiple users U_i are mandate responsible to give the answer of the challenges that was sent by the cloud server (verifier) V . If the user U_i does not give answer, it means that the user has no proof of ownership and it is understand that users are not genuine and trusted. Farther more that users are trying with their own forged proof to reach to the server. For example, a group of malicious users want to interact with the documents by just forwarding a forged ownership proof to the server . In such a case the server V are mandate to verify the multiparty ownership of the encrypted file F . The main aim of PMOW protocol is to detect the misbehavior of the users whenever someone wants to cheat with their forged proof of ownership.

Conclusions

Key Management in Cloud Computing:

The key management is the main & critical task in cloud computing that is the ability to secure, correctly assign, and monitor keys and is used when implementation of encryption is done. To wipe out the problem of a traditional tree-based key management hierarchy, The proposed tree-based key derivation hierarchy allowed the outsourcing party to access the data block located at a specified node, while not being able to access the data blocks encrypted with child keys. An encryption scheme for a two-tier system was presented to achieve flexible and fine-grained access control in the cloud. Most of the computation intensive tasks were delegated to cloud servers without leaking private data. As the data is usually encrypted before being out sourced to cloud servers, how to search the encrypted data in the cloud has recently gained attention and led to the development of searchable encryption techniques. This problem is challenging. The proposed construction is much more efficient from the point of view of both the data owner and the cloud servers. it is important to check remote data integrity (RIC). A privacy-preserving RIC protocol was proposed. The proposed protocol achieved public verifiability without disclosing any information. The experimental results indicated that the proposed scheme is efficient especially when the size of the data file is large or the integrity check is frequent. Proof of ownership (POW) is another security issue related to cloud data storage. An innovative **PMOW** scheme for proof of multiparty ownership with the encrypted data was proposed. Every user can prove to the server that he holds the plaintext of the encrypted file when the server stores one ciphertext only.

Future Work:

How to develop an efficient dynamic suitable POR schemes is still a live problem. Apart

from this how to prohibit malicious cloud users from wrong using of different cloud resources is still a security issue for instance malicious data hosting , bonnet command and control etc. One way to fix this problem is to monitor the cloud resource usage must be strictly; however this is inevitably in conflict with legal users' privacy rights. Further research is needed.

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